

Positive-negative ghost imaging and its optical encryption

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We study the reconstruction algorithm effect on the positive and negative ghost imaging (GI). By introducing three GI algorithms (logarithmic GI, exponential GI and trigonometric GI), we perform numerical simulations and experiments with different GI algorithms, which demonstrate that a positive or negative ghost image can be recovered by modulating the monotonicity of the bucket object signal function. Furthermore, we propose a positive-negative optical encryption scheme based on trigonometric GI. Our work not only broadens the positive-negative GI principle but also paves a way to its applications in optical encryption.

I. INTRODUCTION

Ghost imaging (GI) is an indirect imaging modality which obtains the object information from the intensity fluctuation correlation of two beams: One interacting with object is bucket detected by a single-pixel detector; the other carrying no object information is detected by a spatially resolved multi-pixel detector. In 1995, the first GI experiment was achieved by using the entangled photon pairs generated from spontaneous parametric down-conversion process [1]. Later, pseudo-thermal and thermal light sources were successfully applied to reconstruct ghost images [2–8], which raised a debate on whether GI is a quantum or classical phenomenon. Besides the debate on fundamental physics, GI with different sources and related potential applications attracted considerable research interests, such as visible and infrared sources for remote sensing and turbulence-free detection [9–14], X-ray and fluorescent sources for medical imaging [15–19], etc. Meanwhile, in order to steer GI towards practical applications, high imaging quality and efficiency are in great demand, which sparked lots of studies on the GI reconstruction algorithms, including high-order ghost imaging (HGI) [20–29], differential GI [30], compressive ghost imaging (CGI) [31], etc.

Apart from improving GI efficiency, different GI algorithms also significantly affect the type of a recovered ghost image. For example, a conditional-averaging GI algorithm would generate either a positive or negative ghost image [10, 32–38]. Nevertheless, the imaging reconstruction algorithm effect on positive and negative GI have not been systematically analysed so far, least of all for related potential applications.

In this work, we study the positive and negative GI principle by investigating the reconstruction algorithm

effect. We here introduce three GI algorithms, i.e., logarithmic ghost imaging (LGI), exponential ghost imaging (EGI), and trigonometric ghost imaging (TGI). We theoretically and experimentally compare them with previous algorithms in their positive and negative GI processes. Simulated and experimental results show that a positive or negative ghost image can be recovered by modulating the monotonicity of the bucket object signal function in each algorithm. Furthermore, an optical encryption with trigonometric GI is proposed and tested on the basis of the positive-negative GI principle.

II. THEORETICAL AND SIMULATED ANALYSIS ON POSITIVE AND NEGATIVE GHOST IMAGING

Generally, the second-order correlation function of two fields is defined as [39]

$$G^{(2)}(r_1, r_2) = \langle I(r_1)I(r_2) \rangle, \quad (1)$$

where $I(r_1)$ and $I(r_2)$ are the instantaneous intensities at positions r_1 and r_2 , respectively. $\langle \dots \rangle$ stands for ensemble average. For simplicity, only the spatial correlation is taken into consideration here, but the following results and discussions are also valid for the temporal one. Basically, the image reconstruction of GI originates from the distribution of $G^{(2)}(r_1, r_2)$ values in the space, manifesting a unified approach between GI and HBT experiment [40, 41]. Similar to the critical role of the wave source in HBT experiment, different types of source will result in either a positive or negative ghost image. For chaotic bosons and fermions, the second-order correlation function in Eq. (1) can be further expanded as [42–44]

$$G^{(2)}(r_1, r_2) = G^{(1)}(r_1, r_1)G^{(1)}(r_2, r_2) \pm |G^{(1)}(r_1, r_2)|^2, \quad (2)$$

where $G^{(1)}(r_i, r_j)$ ($i, j = 1, 2$) represents the first-order correlation function, and $+$ and $-$ are for the bosonic and fermionic sources, respectively. In HBT experi-

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ment, $+|G^{(1)}(r_1, r_2)|^2$ leads to a bunching effect, whereas $-|G^{(1)}(r_1, r_2)|^2$ results in an anti-bunching behaviour. Correspondingly, in GI, a bosonic source provides a positive (bright) ghost image, whereas a fermionic source offers a negative (dark) one [43, 44].

Despite different source type, sources with different statistical distribution will also affect the GI type [45]. For the pseudo-thermal / thermal light and entangled photon pairs from spontaneous parametric down-conversion, the sources are governed by super-Poissonian statistics with a statistical distribution $\Delta n_p^2 > \langle n_p \rangle$, where n_p is the particle number and $\Delta n_p^2 = \langle n_p^2 \rangle - \langle n_p \rangle^2$ is the mean-square deviation of n_p . These super-Poissonian sources will generate positive ghost images. In the opposite case, when source obeys sub-Poissonian statistics, i.e., $\Delta n_p^2 < \langle n_p \rangle$, an anti-bunching behaviour will appear, resulting in a negative ghost image. As a Poissonian source brings no intensity fluctuation, i.e., $\Delta n_p^2 = \langle n_p \rangle$, no ghost image can be obtained.

In addition to the source effect above, different GI algorithms can also determine if a positive or negative ghost image is recovered. Assuming that the source is a bosonic one and obeys super-Poissonian statistics, we will focus on the impact of GI algorithms on the positive and negative GI in the following.

According to Eq. (1), the traditional second-order GI reconstruction algorithm can be expressed as

$$G^{(2)}(x, y) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N I_{o_i} I_i(x, y), \quad (3)$$

where I_{o_i} is the bucket intensity signal of object beam, and $I_i(x, y)$ is the spatial intensity distribution of reference beam in the i th measurement. The schematic setup of GI is shown in Fig. 1(a). Usually, a DC-component of object beam is subtracted from the correlation function to provide a better GI quality without background noise. Then Eq. (3) develops into the form as

$$G^{(2)}(x, y) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (I_{o_i} - \overline{I_o}) I_i(x, y), \quad (4)$$

where $\overline{I_o}$ is the average intensity of bucket object signal over N measurements. Based on Eq. (3), in order to achieve positive and negative ghost images, the bucket object signals are divided into two sets [10, 32–38]: for I_{o_i} satisfying $I_{o_i} \geq \overline{I_o}$, Eq. (3) provides a positive ghost image; for I_{o_i} satisfying $I_{o_i} < \overline{I_o}$, a negative ghost image appears. Differently, after subtracting a DC-component as Eq. (4), the pure intensity fluctuation always gives a positive ghost image. To obtain a negative one, $(I_{o_i} - \overline{I_o})$ should take an opposite sign, i.e., $(\overline{I_o} - I_{o_i})$, in Eq. (4).

In comparison to the conditional-averaging GI above, HGI algorithm reconstructs the positive and negative ghost images based on its power index value. The most-

FIG. 1. Schematic setup of traditional ghost imaging.

used form of HGI algorithm is given as [23, 25, 27, 29]

$$G^{(p,q)}(x, y) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (I_{o_i})^p (I_i(x, y))^q, \quad (5)$$

where p and q are the power indices of the bucket object signal and reference signal, respectively. Usually, p and q are positive integers which offer a positive ghost image. A recent study shows that p and q can even take negative and fractional values [46]. When $p \times q < 0$, a negative ghost image can be recovered.

Besides two approaches above, LGI and EGI algorithms are introduced here to study the positive and negative ghost images. We define the LGI algorithm as

$$G^{log}(x, y) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \left(\log_A \frac{I_{o_i}}{\overline{I_o}} \right) I_i(x, y), \quad (6)$$

where A is the base of the logarithmic function. The other algorithm, EGI, is defined as

$$G^{exp}(x, y) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N B^{C \cdot (I_{o_i} / SX_i)} I_i(x, y), \quad (7)$$

where B is the base of the exponential function, C is a constant depending on the value of base B , and SX_i is the total intensity of reference beam $I_i(x, y)$ in the i th measurement, i.e., $SX_i = \int I_i(x, y) dx dy$. Different from previous algorithms, LGI and EGI use their base value to control the GI type. When the base value is greater (smaller) than 1, a positive (negative) ghost image is achieved.

Moreover, another algorithm, TGI, can also achieve the positive and negative GI. For example, we define the TGI in a sinusoidal form as

$$G^{sin}(x, y) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \sin \left[(n + I_{o_i}' - \frac{1}{2}) \pi \right] I_i(x, y), \quad (8)$$

where $I_{o_i}' = (I_{o_i} - I_{min}) / (I_{max} - I_{min})$, and I_{max} and I_{min} are the maximum and minimum of I_{o_i} , respectively.

FIG. 2. Simulated positive and negative ghost images with different algorithms: (a) Object, (b) and (h) traditional ghost imaging, (c) and (i) traditional ghost imaging without DC background, (d) and (j) high-order ghost imaging, (e) and (k) logarithmic ghost imaging, (f) and (l) exponential ghost imaging, (g) and (m) trigonometric ghost imaging

In TGI, n takes even (odd) integers leading to a positive (negative) ghost image.

Figure 2 shows the simulation results of positive and negative GI with different algorithms. A grayscale boat picture (101×101 pixels) acts as the imaging object, as shown in Fig. 2(a). In the simulation, we set $p = 50$ and $q = 1$ for HGI algorithm, because a large p value will increase the image visibility and a small q will suppress the noise dramatically [25, 27, 29]. In both LGI and EGI algorithms, we set base $A, B = 10$ and $A, B = 0.1$ for the positive and negative GI processes, respectively. And constant $C = 1$ is taken in the EGI case. In TGI algorithms, $n = 0$ is set for positive GI, and $n = 1$ is set for negative GI. The measurement number is 80,000 for all algorithms. Here, we employ peak signal-to-noise ratio (PSNR) to estimate the image quality, which is defined as

$$\text{PSNR} = 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{\text{MAX}^2}{\text{MSE}} \right), \quad (9)$$

where $\text{MAX}=255$ is the maximum possible pixel value of the image. MSE is the mean square error, given by $\frac{1}{m_1 \times m_2} \sum_{i,j} [T_{re}(x_i, y_j) - T(x_i, y_j)]^2$, where $m_1 \times m_2$ is the pixel number, $T_{re}(x_i, y_j)$ and $T(x_i, y_j)$ are the pixel values of the recovered image and the object, respectively.

Figures 2(b) and 2(h) show the positive and negative images recovered from the conditional-averaging GI, respectively. Since only half signals ($I_{o_i} > \bar{I}_o$ or $I_{o_i} < \bar{I}_o$) are available for the reconstruction calculations, the imaging quality is worse than GI with the DC-component subtracted, and also worse than LGI, N-GI and TGI. Although HGI algorithm can also obtain the positive and negative images shown in Figs. 2(d) and 2(j), it has a low imaging efficiency. It is because that a high order correlation on bucket intensity signal will enhance the information signal but at the same time increase the DC background noise. This low efficiency however can be improved by replacing the bucket object

signal $(I_{o_i})^p$ with a DC-component subtracted one, i.e. $(I_{o_i})^p - (\bar{I}_o)^p$. The comparison between different algorithms in Fig. 2 manifests that EGI offers a better quality, and GI without DC-component, LGI and TGI have a similar reconstruction efficiency both in the positive and negative GI processes.

GI Algorithms	Positive GI	Negative GI
GI: $\langle I_o \cdot I(x, y) \rangle$	$I_o (I_o \geq \bar{I}_o)$	$I_o (I_o < \bar{I}_o)$
GI no DC: $\langle (I_o - \bar{I}_o) \cdot I(x, y) \rangle$	$I_o - \bar{I}_o$	$\bar{I}_o - I_o$
HGI: $\langle (I_o)^p \cdot (I(x, y))^q \rangle$	$p \cdot q > 0$	$p \cdot q < 0$
LGI: $\langle (\log_A I_o / \bar{I}_o) \cdot I(x, y) \rangle$	$A > 1$	$A < 1$
EGI: $\langle B^{C \cdot (I_o / SX)} \cdot I(x, y) \rangle$	$B^C > 1$	$B^C < 1$
TGI: $\langle \sin[(n + I_o' - 1/2)\pi] \cdot I(x, y) \rangle$	n is even	n is odd

TABLE I. Parameters to generate positive and negative ghost images in different algorithms.

To clearly reveal the positive and negative GI principle, the bucket object signals (50 measurements) of different algorithms are presented in Fig. 3. According to the definition of GI, reference signal $I_i(x, y)$ and bucket object signal I_{o_i} are one-to-one match. In order to improve the imaging reconstruction efficiency, different functions $f(I_{o_i})$ are usually introduced to replace the bucket object signal. No matter what specific form $f(I_{o_i})$ takes, the type of ghost image is determined by the monotonicity of $f(I_{o_i})$. If $f(I_{o_i})$ is monotonically increasing (decreasing) as I_{o_i} increases, a positive (negative) image will be obtained. From Figs. 3a, 3b and 3d, when the power index $p > 0$ in HGI, the base value $A > 1$ in LGI, and $n = 0$ in TGI, it clearly shows that $f(I_{o_i})$ intensity functions have the same variation trend as original bucket object signal I_{o_i} , leading to positive images. On the contrary, when $p < 0$, $A < 1$ and $n = 1$, a completely opposite trend of $f(I_{o_i})$ exhibits, resulting in negative images. Particularly, in EGI algorithm, I_{o_i}/SX_i acts as

FIG. 3. Simulated intensity signals with different ghost imaging algorithms: (a) high-order ghost imaging, (b) logarithmic ghost imaging, (c) exponential ghost imaging, and (d) trigonometric ghost imaging.

the power index. Since SX_i always changes with the measuring times i , $f(Io_i) = B^{Io_i/SX_i}$ does not follow a strict monotonicity to Io_i , as shown in Fig. 3c. Nevertheless, the overall trend of $f(Io_i)$ in EGI is determined by the base value as discussed in LGI case above. This non-strict monotonicity of EGI is similar to the differential GI algorithm with $f(Io_i) = Io_i - \bar{Io} \cdot SX_i/S\bar{X}_i$ [30], which may explain a better imaging quality of EGI shown in Fig. 2. Table I summarizes the parameters used in different algorithms to achieve positive and negative ghost images. Compared to the monotonicity-dependent principle, conditional-averaging GI works well in the basic GI definition $\langle IoI(x,y) \rangle$, but is ineffective in DC-subtracted GI, LGI, EGI and TGI algorithms, due to its background-dependent nature. Moreover, it should be mentioned that, we here only discuss the monotonicity of the bucket object signal function $f(Io_i)$. Alternatively, one can keep the bucket object signal Io_i unchanged and modulate the monotonicity of the reference signal $I_i(x,y)$ to determine if a positive or negative ghost image is recovered. In addition, since all discussions above are based on a photonic source with super-Poissonian statistics, the principle of monotonicity dependence above will lead to an opposite result for a bosonic source with sub-Poissonian statistics or a chaotic fermionic source.

To further understand the monotonicity-dependent principle on positive and negative GI, we can go back to the definition of GI. In Eq. 3, the reconstructed image $G^{(2)}(x,y)$ can be viewed as a Fourier expansion, where the reference signal $I_i(x,y)$ represents the base and the bucket signal Io_i represents corresponding coefficient as $Io_i = \sum_{x=1}^{m_1} \sum_{y=1}^{m_2} O(x,y) I_i(x,y)$, and $O(x,y)$ is the original object image function. As a simplest case, we here suppose that the original image only consists of two pixels, i.e., $[O(1,1), O(1,2)]$, and the reference signals are mutually orthogonal, i.e., $I_1(x,y) = [1,0]$ and $I_2(x,y) = [0,1]$. Therefore, according to Eq. 3, one can

easily obtain that $G^{(2)}(x,y) = [O(1,1), O(1,2)]/2$ after two measurements. Suppose $O(1,1) > O(1,2)$ in original image, $G^{(2)}(x,y)$ thereby recovers a positive image. Now, if we replace Io_i with $f(Io_i)$, the reconstructed image will be $G^{(2)}(x,y) = [f(O(1,1)), f(O(1,2))]/2$. Due to the monotonicity-dependent principle, $G^{(2)}(x,y)$ will obtain a positive (negative) ghost image when $f(Io_i)$ is a monotonic increasing (decreasing) function. Note that, in mathematics, the bases in Fourier expansion should be always mutually orthogonal. But in GI, the bases are random light speckles, which are usually non-orthogonal. These non-orthogonal bases will make Io_i complicated, which however will not affect the validity of the monotonicity-dependent principle when measurement number N is large enough. A more complicated 2×2 pixels case with non-orthogonal bases is discussed in Appendix.

III. EXPERIMENTS ON POSITIVE AND NEGATIVE GHOST IMAGING WITH DIFFERENT ALGORITHMS

FIG. 4. Experimental setup of computational ghost imaging.

FIG. 5. Experimental positive and negative ghost images with different algorithms: (a) Object, (b) and (h) traditional ghost imaging, (c) and (i) traditional ghost imaging without DC background, (d) and (j) high-order ghost imaging, (e) and (k) logarithmic ghost imaging, (f) and (l) exponential ghost imaging, (g) and (m) trigonometric ghost imaging. (n)-(s) Ghost images obtained from subtracting the negative one from the corresponding positive one.

All GI algorithms above can work within the traditional second-order GI experimental framework. Compared to the traditional GI setup shown in Fig. 1, computational GI introduces a known random matrix $X_i^{m_1 \times m_2}$ to replace the reference beam $I_i(x, y)$ [47]. Since the random matrix $X_i^{m_1 \times m_2}$ can be generated by a liquid-crystal spatial light modulators, digital micromirror devices or projectors [13, 47–50], only a single-pixel detector is enough for computational GI experiment. By employing the computational GI scheme, we experimentally test the imaging algorithm effect on positive and negative GI below. Our experimental setup is shown in Fig. 4. A standard projector with 1024×768 pixels is used to generate the random matrices. For simplicity, an independent speckle consists of 16×16 pixels among total 1024×768 pixels, so there are only 64×48 speckles in one frame [37]. After reflected by the object (a model of airplane), the reflected beam is bucket collected by a single-pixel detector, where $l_1 = 70$ cm and $l_2 = 100$ cm. The exposure time of the detector is 400 ms, and the sampling number is 23000 in the experiment.

Figure 5 shows the experimental ghost images recovered from different GI algorithms. Consistent with the simulation results in Fig. 2, one can see that the imaging quality of HGI and conditional-averaging GI is worse than other algorithms. It should be noted that, for the same set of measurement data, the PSNR values of positive and negative ghost images in DC-subtracted GI, are the same. It is because that the only difference between their bucket object signal function $f(I_{o_i})$ is an opposite sign, i.e., $f_P(I_{o_i}) = (I_{o_i} - \bar{I}_o) = -f_N(I_{o_i})$. This is also the case for LGI, i.e., $f_P(I_{o_i}) = \log_{10}(I_{o_i}/\bar{I}_o) = -\log_{0.1}(I_{o_i}/\bar{I}_o) = -f_N(I_{o_i})$, and TGI, i.e., $f_P(I_{o_i}) = \sin[(0 + I_{o_i} - 1/2)\pi] = -\sin[(1 + I_{o_i} - 1/2)\pi] = -f_N(I_{o_i})$. After normalizing the positive and negative GI images respectively, we fur-

ther perform an operation, i.e., subtracting the negative image from the corresponding positive one. As shown in Figs. 5(n)-(s), the qualities of subtracted ghost images in conditional-averaging GI, HGI, and EGI, have been improved. This phenomenon has been reported and discussed in conditional-averaging GI [10, 32–38]. Different from conditional-averaging GI, this normalized subtraction operation in HGI and EGI effectively suppress the noise in their divergence reconstruction calculations, which therefore increases the image quality. Since the positive and negative ghost images have the same PSNR values in DC-subtracted GI, LGI and TGI as mentioned above, there are no improvements in these three algorithms by applying the subtraction operation.

IV. OPTICAL ENCRYPTION SCHEME USING POSITIVE AND NEGATIVE GHOST IMAGING

Optical encryption is an important application of GI, especially the computational GI which employs the active illumination with known random masks [48]. Based on the analysis of positive and negative GI above, we propose an optical encryption and test with simulation in the following. As shown in Fig. 6(a), a step-by-step encryption flow is given as:

1. Alice wants to send a piece of original information “71” to Bob. For safety consideration, Alice firstly separate “71” into two images “OR” and “LF”.
2. By using TGI algorithm, Alice encodes “OR” and “LF” separately with random matrix keys $\{X^{m_1 \times m_2}\}$.
3. Alice sends Bob the random matrix keys $\{X^{m_1 \times m_2}\}$ and encoded intensity signal-

s $\{t(n_1, I_o^a)\}$ and $\{t(n_2, I_o^b)\}$ over a public channel.

- After receiving the random matrix keys and two encoded intensity signals, Bob uses their pre-agreed algorithm TGI (a sinusoidal function here) to recover the information “71”, by adding $\{t(n_1, I_o^a)\}$ and $\{t(n_2, I_o^b)\}$ together.

During the optical encryption process, integer n_1 in $\{t(n_1, I_o^a)\}$ should be even which encodes a positive “OR” image; Whereas integer n_2 in $\{t(n_2, I_o^b)\}$ should be odd which encodes a negative “LF” image. This positive-negative GI encryption scheme divides one bucket signal into two, increasing the difficulty in encoding process but at the same time enhancing the security of the optical encryption based on GI. What’s more, TGI algorithm also plays an important role in the encryption. Suppose Eve, an eavesdropper, has stolen all encoded intensity signals and random matrix keys. By using the conventional GI algorithm to decode the information, Eve will obtain noise as shown in Fig. 6(a). It is because that Alice can choose different even (or odd) n_1 (or n_2) values in different measurements which will make the bucket signal become random for other GI algorithms except the sinusoidal function in TGI.

By considering the periodic characteristics of bucket signal $f(I_o_i)$ of TGI, we can further develop it into $f(I_o_i) = \sin[d(n + I_o'_i - 1/2)\pi]$ to increase the security of positive-negative GI encryption scheme, where d is added to modulate the period of $f(I_o_i)$. As shown in Fig. 6(b), a step-by-step encryption flow is given below:

- Alice wants to send a piece of original information “71” to Bob. She firstly separate “71” into two images “OR” and “LF”.
- By using TGI algorithm, Alice separately encodes “OR” and “LF” as $\{t(n_1, I_o^a)\}$ and $\{t(n_2, I_o^b)\}$, respectively, with random matrix keys $\{X^{m_1 \times m_2}\}$.
- Alice applies pre-agreed numbers $d_1 = 567$, $d_2 = 0.01$ and $d_3 = 123$ to two encoded signals, and obtains two new encoded signals as $\{d_3 t(n_1, I_o^a)\}$ and $\{d_1 t(n_1, I_o^a) + d_2 t(n_2, I_o^b)\}$.
- Alice sends Bob the random matrix keys $\{X^{m_1 \times m_2}\}$ and two new encoded signals $\{d_3 t(n_1, I_o^a)\}$ and $\{d_1 t(n_1, I_o^a) + d_2 t(n_2, I_o^b)\}$ over a public channel.
- After receiving the random matrix keys and two encoded intensity signals, Bob uses pre-agreed number d_3 to obtain $\{t(n_1, I_o^a)\}$, and then uses d_1 and d_2 to obtain $\{t(n_2, I_o^b)\}$.
- After retrieving $\{t(n_1, I_o^a)\}$ and $\{t(n_2, I_o^b)\}$, Bob can employ TGI algorithm (a sinusoidal function here) to recover the information “71”, by adding $\{t(n_1, I_o^a)\}$ and $\{t(n_2, I_o^b)\}$ together.

FIG. 6. Scheme of the encryption scheme based on (a) positive-negative ghost imaging and trigonometric ghost imaging algorithm, (b) positive-negative ghost imaging and trigonometric ghost imaging algorithm with period modulation. In all simulation, the objects and binary random matrices are 85×67 pixels, and the measuring numbers are set as 20,000. In trigonometric ghost imaging algorithm, $\{t(n, I_o)\} = \{(n + I_o' - 0.5)\pi\}$, and n_1 (or n_2) can take different even (or odd) integers for different measurements.

Here, we assume that d_1 , d_2 and d_3 are three pre-agreed numbers between Alice and Bob, so Alice don't need to send them to Bob. Suppose again Eve has stolen all encoded intensity signals and random matrix keys during the communications, and successfully guess the sinusoidal function out in decoding process. Without knowing the values of d_1 , d_2 and d_3 , Eve cannot obtain

the encoded images as shown in Fig. 6(b). By testing different number D values to decode two encoded signals $\{d_3t(n_1, Io^a)\}$ and $\{d_1t(n_1, Io^a) + d_2t(n_2, Io^b)\}$, Eve can only recover the image of “OR”. Assuming that Eve even knows all the rules in our encryption, Eve will use two numbers D_1 and D_2 to extract the other hidden image (i.e., “LF”). From Fig. 6(b), one can see that “LF” can be successfully retrieved only when $D_1 = 1/d_1 = 1/567$ and $D_2 = 1/d_3 = 1/123$. A slight deviation between D_1 and $1/d_1$ (or D_2 and $1/d_3$) will obtain image of “OR” instead of “LF”. It clearly indicates that the security of optical encryption based on computational GI is largely enhanced by our TGI and positive-negative GI scheme.

V. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, we studied the positive and negative GI by analysing the imaging reconstruction algorithm effect. We introduced three GI algorithms and compared them with other different GI algorithms in simulation and experiment, which manifested that a positive or negative ghost image could be recovered by modulating the monotonicity of the bucket object signal function. According to this positive and negative GI principle, an optical encryption with the computational GI scheme was further proposed and tested, which would broaden the way to the applications of GI.

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VII. APPENDIX

As an example, an image with 2×2 pixels case is discussed below. The original object image function is

$$O(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} O(1, 1) & O(1, 2) \\ O(2, 1) & O(2, 2) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (10)$$

Suppose the reference signals are random binary matrices, there are 16 possible non-orthogonal bases with the

same probability of occurrence during the measurement:

$$I(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \\ \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \\ \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \\ \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (11)$$

After 16 measurements with different reference signals above, one can obtain the reconstructed ghost image as

$$G^{(2)}(x, y) = \frac{1}{16} \begin{bmatrix} G^{(2)}(1, 1) & G^{(2)}(1, 2) \\ G^{(2)}(2, 1) & G^{(2)}(2, 2) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (12)$$

where

$$G^{(2)}(1, 1) = f[O(1, 1)] + f[O(1, 1) + O(1, 2)] \\ + f[O(1, 1) + O(2, 1)] + f[O(1, 1) + O(2, 2)] \\ + f[O(1, 1) + O(1, 2) + O(2, 1)] \\ + f[O(1, 1) + O(1, 2) + O(2, 2)] \\ + f[O(1, 1) + O(2, 1) + O(2, 2)] \\ + f[O(1, 1) + O(1, 2) + O(2, 1) + O(2, 2)], \quad (13)$$

$$G^{(2)}(1, 2) = f[O(1, 2)] + f[O(1, 2) + O(1, 1)] \\ + f[O(1, 2) + O(2, 1)] + f[O(1, 2) + O(2, 2)] \\ + f[O(1, 2) + O(1, 1) + O(2, 1)] \\ + f[O(1, 2) + O(1, 1) + O(2, 2)] \\ + f[O(1, 2) + O(2, 1) + O(2, 2)] \\ + f[O(1, 1) + O(1, 2) + O(2, 1) + O(2, 2)], \quad (14)$$

$$G^{(2)}(2, 1) = f[O(2, 1)] + f[O(2, 1) + O(1, 1)] \\ + f[O(2, 1) + O(1, 2)] + f[O(2, 1) + O(2, 2)] \\ + f[O(2, 1) + O(1, 1) + O(1, 2)] \\ + f[O(2, 1) + O(1, 1) + O(2, 2)] \\ + f[O(2, 1) + O(1, 2) + O(2, 2)] \\ + f[O(1, 1) + O(1, 2) + O(2, 1) + O(2, 2)], \quad (15)$$

$$G^{(2)}(2, 2) = f[O(2, 2)] + f[O(2, 2) + O(1, 1)] \\ + f[O(2, 2) + O(1, 2)] + f[O(2, 2) + O(2, 1)] \\ + f[O(2, 2) + O(1, 1) + O(1, 2)] \\ + f[O(2, 2) + O(1, 1) + O(2, 1)] \\ + f[O(2, 2) + O(1, 2) + O(2, 1)] \\ + f[O(1, 1) + O(1, 2) + O(2, 1) + O(2, 2)]. \quad (16)$$

By assuming $O(1,1) > O(1,2) > O(2,1) > O(2,2)$ in original object image function, one can clearly see that $G^{(2)}(1,1) > G^{(2)}(1,2) > G^{(2)}(2,1) > G^{(2)}(2,2)$ (or $G^{(2)}(1,1) < G^{(2)}(1,2) < G^{(2)}(2,1) < G^{(2)}(2,2)$) for a

monotonic increasing (or decreasing) function $f[O(x,y)]$, after comparing Eq.13-16. It means that a positive (or negative) ghost image can be obtained by following our monotonicity-dependent principle.

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